

ANAPHYLAXIS IN CHILDREN: MECHANISMS OF DEVELOPMENT AND MODERN TRENDS IN INTENSIVE THERAPY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14184337>

Аннотация. Анафилаксия ҳаёт учун хавф солувчи, зудлик билан таъхисланиши лозим бўлган, тез тарқалувчи алергик реакциядир. Анафилаксия ва анафилактик шок (АШ) бир биридан гемодинамик ўзгаришларнинг кузатилиши билан фарқланади. Анафилаксия ва анафилактик шокнинг болаларда ўзига хос диагностик мезонлари ва клиник белгилари мавжуд. Анафилаксия/АШ ни даволашда адреналин препаратини белгиланган тартибда юбориш самарали ҳисобланиди, шунингдек, кристаллоид эритмалар, глюкокортикоидлар, антигистамин препаратлари ва сальбутамолни қўллаш мумкин.

Калит сўзлар: анафилаксия, анафилактик шок, гипотония, бронхоспазм, эритема.

Аннотация. Анафилаксия — опасная для жизни, быстро распространяющаяся аллергическая реакция, требующая немедленной диагностики. Анафилаксия и анафилактический шок (АШ) отличаются друг от друга наблюдением гемодинамических изменений. Анафилаксия и анафилактический шок у детей имеют специфические диагностические критерии и клинические симптомы. Установлено, что при лечении анафилаксии/АШ эффективным является введение адреналина, а также кристаллоидных растворов, глюкокортикоидов, антигистаминных препаратов и сальбутамола.

Ключевые слова: анафилаксия, анафилактический шок, гипотония, бронхоспазм, эритема.

Abstract. Anaphylaxis is a life-threatening, rapidly progressing allergic reaction that requires urgent diagnosis. Anaphylaxis and anaphylactic shock (AS) are differentiated by the presence of hemodynamic changes. There are specific diagnostic criteria and clinical signs of anaphylaxis and anaphylactic shock in children. The administration of adrenaline according to the prescribed regimen is considered effective in the treatment of anaphylaxis/AS, along with the possible use of crystalloid solutions, glucocorticoids, antihistamines, and salbutamol.

Keywords: Anaphylaxis, anaphylactic shock, hypotension, bronchospasm, erythema.

Anaphylaxis is a rapidly spreading, multi-system allergic reaction that manifests with hypotension or bronchospasm, erythema or angioedema, as well as persistent gastrointestinal symptoms, and is a life-threatening emergency.

IgE-mediated anaphylactic reactions involve allergic mechanisms, while anaphylactoid reactions are non-IgE-dependent. These two terms have recently been unified under the diagnosis of anaphylaxis [3,4,9].

Anaphylaxis is diagnosed clinically when any one of the following acute manifestations occurs: typical skin conditions, respiratory distress, cardiovascular compromise (hypotension), gastrointestinal symptoms such as abdominal pain or vomiting, as well as hypotension, bronchospasm, and upper airway obstruction.

Anaphylactic shock (AS) is an acute circulatory failure resulting from anaphylaxis, characterized by a systolic blood pressure (SBP) of less than 90 mm Hg. The diagnosis of shock

requires the presence of specific hemodynamic disturbances. For example, life-threatening bronchospasm along with urticaria can occur in anaphylaxis, but it does not constitute anaphylactic shock.

Etiological factors include drug reactions (31.2-46.5%), food products (23.3-31%), and insect venom (14.9-20%), which can lead to life-threatening anaphylaxis. The frequency of anaphylaxis occurs at a rate of 1.5-7.9 per 100,000 population annually. The type of trigger depends on the patient's age, with food products most often being the cause in children, according to research by F. Simons et al.

Anaphylaxis is typically an IgE-mediated hypersensitivity reaction that occurs after repeated exposure to a specific antigen (allergen). During anaphylaxis, numerous chemical mediators, such as histamine, leukotrienes, and prostaglandins, are released. These mediators are products of the degranulation of mast cells and basophils, which play a central role in the allergic response. As a result of the binding of IgE to high-affinity receptors (FcεRI) on mast cells and basophils, and subsequent receptor aggregation, biologically active substances such as histamine, tryptase, carboxypeptidase A, and proteoglycans are released within a short period of time. [5]. Valenta et al. According to his research, phospholipase A₂ (PLA₂) produces metabolites of arachidonic acid as a result of activation of cyclooxygenases and lipoxygenases. The physiology of these chemical mediators is as follows: histamine increases vascular permeability and vasodilation, leading to tissue hypoperfusion and increased heart rate. Prostaglandin D causes bronchoconstriction and constricts pulmonary arteries while dilating peripheral vessels, thus reducing blood supply to vital organs. Leukotrienes enhance bronchospasm and vascular permeability, and platelet-activating factor contributes to bronchoconstriction and increased vessel permeability.

According to Gell and Coombs classification, Type I hypersensitivity reactions occur via IgE on the surface of mast cells and basophils.

Table 1.
Diagnostic Criteria for Anaphylaxis

№	Clinical Features	Duration
1.	Acute onset of disease: -Respiratory disorders Damage to the skin and mucous membranes -Arterial hypotension	From several minutes to several hours
2.	The development of two or more clinical signs under the influence of an allergen: - Damage to the skin and mucous membranes - Respiratory disorders - Arterial hypotension -Symptoms of gastrointestinal disorders	From several minutes to several hours
3.	arterial hypotension	From several minutes to several hours

There are different classifications of anaphylactic shock (AS) based on the severity of hemodynamic disturbances, the rate of development, and clinical manifestations.

By severity:

Grade 1 AS: In this stage, hemodynamic disturbances are not pronounced. Arterial blood pressure (ABP) decreases by 30-40 mm Hg, but the patient remains conscious. Symptoms may include ringing in the ears, headache, coughing, redness of the skin, and signs of rhinitis and conjunctivitis.

Grade 2: In this stage, hemodynamic disturbances are significant, with ABP dropping to 90–60/40 mmHg or lower, and the patient may lose consciousness. Signs include muffled heart tones, tachycardia, tachyarrhythmia, vomiting, pale or cyanotic skin, stridor, wheezing, and crackles in the lungs.

Grade 3: In this stage, there is a complete loss of consciousness, and ABP drops to 60–40/0 mmHg. The patient may show signs of shock, dilated pupils, cyanosis of the lips, muffled heart sounds, and a weak or threadlike pulse.

Grade 4: In this most severe stage, no measurable ABP is found. Circulatory collapse and cessation of respiration occur, requiring urgent cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) [1].

According to studies by Simons F., Arduoso L., Bilò M. et al., if the first signs of hypotension in children include increased tachycardia, Lieberman P., Nicklas R., Oppenheimer J. et al. define hypotension in children as follows:

For children aged 1 month to 1 year, hypotension is defined as systolic blood pressure (SBP) < 70 mm Hg.

For children aged 1 to 10 years, hypotension is defined as systolic blood pressure (SBP) < 70 mm Hg + (2 × age in years).

For children aged 11 to 17 years, hypotension is defined as systolic blood pressure (SBP) < 90 mm Hg.

The development of anaphylaxis or AS is described through the presence of at least one of the following diagnostic criteria (Table 1):

Acute onset of disease with skin and mucosal changes, bronchospasm, hypoxemia, or hypotension, along with loss of consciousness. Acute and life-threatening disorders of the respiratory or circulatory system that develop after allergen exposure. A drop in ABP following contact with an allergen.

Key Diagnostic Features of Anaphylaxis and AS:

Characteristic features for diagnosing anaphylaxis and AS include the presence of disturbances in multiple systems:

Cardiovascular system: Tachycardia, bradycardia, arrhythmia, hypotension, pallor, cardiac arrest.

Respiratory system: Wheezing, stridor, hoarseness, difficulty speaking, changes in voice, rhinitis, rhinorrhea, persistent coughing, tongue swelling, bronchospasm.

Central nervous system: Dizziness, restlessness, seizures, mydriasis.

Gastrointestinal system: Abdominal pain, nausea, diarrhea, vomiting.

Management of Anaphylaxis/AS:

In severe cases of anaphylaxis or AS, it is critical to urgently transfer the patient to the intensive care unit. The patient should be placed in a supine position with the head turned to one side and the legs elevated. If the child suddenly stands up or sits, death can occur within seconds. Conversely, if the patient experiences bronchospasm or upper airway obstruction, a sitting position is preferred. For unconscious patients, ensuring patency of the upper airways is a priority (Table 2).

Table 2

Emergency Management in Anaphylactic Shock

Steps in Emergency Management	Action
1. Stop allergen exposure	Discontinue exposure to the allergen immediately.
2. Positioning the patient	Lay the patient flat, turn the head to one side, and elevate the legs.
3. Intensive monitoring	Continuous monitoring of vital signs.
4. If respiration and circulation stop:	A) Perform CPR (Cardiopulmonary Resuscitation) B) Administer 0.1% adrenaline (dosage based on age) C) Establish intravenous access D) Administer 0.9% saline at 20 ml/kg
5. Corticosteroids	Administer corticosteroids as appropriate.
6. Once ABP is stabilized	Administer clemastine (0.1%) 25 mcg/kg per day, divided into 2 doses.
7. Continued intensive monitoring	Close monitoring of the patient's condition.
8. Nebulized treatment	Administer salbutamol as indicated, using a nebulizer.

For children with anaphylaxis or AS, adrenaline (0.1% solution) is administered intramuscularly at a dose of 0.01 mg/kg (maximum dose: 0.15 mg/kg for children under 6 years, 0.3 mg for children 6–12 years, and 0.5 mg for adults). If no positive change is observed within 5 minutes, the dose can be repeated. If the patient shows no response after two doses, adrenaline may be given intravenously in a 1:10,000 dilution, with ECG, blood pressure, and respiratory rate monitoring. If no improvement is seen after three doses of adrenaline, a continuous infusion at 0.1 mcg/kg/min (up to 1 mcg/kg/min) may be started.

In children, supplemental oxygen should be provided via a face mask to address hypoxia. For correction of relative hypovolemia, crystalloid solutions are given at a dose of 20 ml/kg [8].

For persistent respiratory symptoms, corticosteroid treatment with methylprednisolone (1–2 mg/kg), hydrocortisone (2–4 mg/kg), or dexamethasone (0.1–0.4 mg/kg) is recommended [7].

Once ABP stabilizes, antihistamines (e.g., clemastine) can be used. Care should be taken when administering intravenous antihistamines, as they can exacerbate hypotension, particularly in children under 35–40 kg body weight. For children, the dose of diphenhydramine (maximum 50 mg) should be carefully calculated. It is impossible to use this drug to newborn babies [2,6].

For children with bronchospasm or a history of asthma, inhaled salbutamol should be used as part of the treatment for anaphylaxis. This can be administered using a metered-dose inhaler (MDI), with 5–10 puffs every 20 minutes until wheezing or respiratory distress resolves.

Conclusion:

The faster anaphylaxis and AS are treated and the more timely the monitoring, the lower the risk of death. Rapid interventions, early diagnosis, and appropriate hospitalization will significantly reduce the severity of outcomes. All children who have experienced anaphylaxis should be under ongoing monitoring by a pediatrician and allergist.

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